

MAGISTRLAR CERTIFICATE

OF ACHIEVEMENT

... PROUDLY ...
PRESENTED TO

Nurjanov Allabergan

BUGDOYNING OZIQLANISH MAYDONIGA QARAB DON YIRIKLIGIGA VA

SIFATIGA TASIRI

WEBSITE: WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

EMAIL: INFO@REANDPUB.UZ

2023/FEVRAL

